

This is the brain set, the set of mental happenings, which goes as followed:

- The emotions, 0th brain paired 0th brain, the extra 0th brain, and the outcome of another 0th brain.
- The thoughts, 1 brain paired 1 brain, the extra 1st brain, and the outcome of another 1st brain.
- The thinking, 2 brain paired 2nd brain, the extra 2nd brain, and the outcome of another 2nd brain.
- The reasons, 3rd brain paired 3rd brain, the extra 3rd brain, and the outcome of another 3rd brain.
- The decisions, 4th brain paired 4th brain, the extra 4th brain, and the outcome of another 4th brain.
- The motivation, 5th brain paired 5th brain, the extra 5th brain, and the outcome of another 5th brain.
- The channel, 6th brain paired 6th brain, the extra 6th brain, and the outcome of another 6th brain.
- The syndrome, 7th brain paired 7th brain, the extra 7th brain, and the outcome of another 7th brain.
- Imagination, 8th brain paired 8 brain, the extra 8th brain, and the outcome of another 8th brain.

Set.